

THE ROLE OF HIDDEN CURRICULUM IN SHAPING ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS CHARACTER

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Abstract

The background this research is the issue of environmental damage globally, so that innovation is needed in increasing the spirit of environmental concern. This study aims to explain the role of hidden curriculum that can shape the character of santri / student environmental awareness. This study uses a qualitative approach with data collection by observation, literature review and interview. The theoretical foundation used is the hidden curriculum theory and pesantren (Islamic boarding schools that care about the environment). The object of this research is Islamic Boarding School of Religion Source (SPMAA) in East Java, Indonesia. This object is based on the facts about the awareness of SPMAA Islamic boarding schools on the surrounding environment such as afforestation, environmentally friendly environmental policies and facilities, processing of independent natural resources and the behavior of students who care about environmental conservation. This study concludes, First, incorporating environmental education into a hidden curriculum is an effective way to shape the character of environmental care from students or students. Second, the SPMAA Pesantren provides a learning model for environmental education based on a hidden curriculum, which is included in several subjects and habituation practices.

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1. Introduction

Human use environmental resources in their day to day life. These resources are renewable and non-renewable. Continuous use of environmental resources without consideration will become environmental degradation. According to The United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction, the definition of environmental degradation is the reduction of the capacity of the environment to meet social and ecological objectives and needs. Environmental degradation is the deterioration of the environment through depletion of natural resources such as air, water, and soil; the destruction of ecosystems and the extinction of wildlife. ¹

Many academics, researchers, and government institutions take measures to reduce environmental degradation. The effort that has been done is the go green campaign, reducing the use of primary plastic materials, saving electricity, discovering new resources such as solar resources, finding substitutes that are environmentally friendly and others.

Although several methods have been carried out, Environmental problems still become one of the major contemporary issues. In other words, an update is needed to overcome this problem. In this article, the author will provide one solution to overcome environmental degradation through education. That is by forming environmental awareness in santri /students.

¹ Swati Tyagi, Neelam Garg and Rajan Paudel, "Environmental Degradation: Causes and Consequences", *European Researcher*, 2014, Vol.(81) :8-2.

Environmental awareness it means being aware of the natural and making choices that benefit- rather than hurt- the earth we live on.²

The curriculum is an essential component in education.³ According to Beauchamp, who was quoted by Muhammad Nurhalim, a curriculum is a written document which may contain many ingredients, but it is a plan for the education of pupils during their enrollment in given school.⁴

The curriculum is divided into two, the actual curriculum and the hidden curriculum. The actual curriculum or functional curriculum is the implementation of the ideal curriculum and is operated in the classroom. While the hidden curriculum is the result of "powerful relations" in the classroom. The practice can be in the form of class leadership patterns, entrepreneurship, courtesy, and class quality. It can take the form of a superstructure, class consciousness, patriarchy, heterosexuality, and others that will form a habitus will shape the character of the santri,

In this article, researchers researched the Sumber Pendidikan Mental Agama Allah (SPMAA) in East Java, Indonesia. Pondok Pesantren implements the learning process by prioritizing environmental awareness.

There are several reasons why research must be carried out in this place: first, Pesantren are Islamic religious education institutions and the learning and nurturing process is carried out in a cottage (dormitory) so that the implementation is continuous and carried out all the time, Secondly, according to the East Java Communication and Information Committee in 2011⁵, SPMAA Pesantren is proposed as a pesantren model that implements a go green school system and has a curriculum. Third, the SPMAA Pesantren conducts the learning process of religious books in which there is an insight into environmental conservation. so that Santri not only know about religious knowledge, but they are also able to practice utilizing the potential and preservation of the environment.

Based on the background of the Pondok Pesantren SPMAA that cares about the environment, it is what makes researchers write this article as a form of innovation from the solution to prevent and overcome environmental degradation through the field of education, especially the hidden curriculum. Innovation solutions offered are effective. The research focuses more on the implementation of life in Pondok Pesantren schools that are environmentally friendly and the impact on character building on environmental awareness for students.

2. Research Methodology

This study used a qualitative approach with data collection techniques by observation, literature review and interview. Source of data onto this research comes from both primary data and secondary data. Primary data constructed from observation, interview and also questionnaire to get direct information about the practice of hidden curriculum on Pondok Pesantren SPMAA. The interview was conducted directly to the residents (Ustadz, Santri, Kiyai and surrounding communities) of the pesantren.

² Nate Sullivan, *Environmental Awareness: Definition, History & Importance*

<https://study.com/academy/lesson/environmental-awareness-definition-history-importance.html>, (Aug, 2018)

³ M. Slamet Yahya, "Hidden Curriculum Pada Sistem Pendidikan Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Negeri (STAIN) Purwokerto Tahun 2013", *Jurnal Kependidikan*, Vol. 1 No. 1 (November, 2013) :123-149

⁴ Muhammad Nurhalim, "Optimalisasi Kurikulum Aktual dan Kurikulum Tersembunyi dalam Kurikulum 2013" *Insania*, Vol. 19, No. 1, (Januari – Juni, 2014) : 115-132

⁵ Kominfo Jawa Timur, *SPMAA Siapkan Kurikulum Eco Pesantren*, <http://kominfo.jatimprov.go.id/read/umum/25505>, (Jan 24, 2011)

The secondary data used to reinforce the findings and complete the information collected through direct interviews for the pesantren which comes from reading sources and various other sources consisting of books, student paper, theses, dissertations, historical studies journals to official documents from various agencies. Data analysis done after using the above data collection techniques is to process and analyze the data by using descriptive-qualitative analysis.

A sampling of this research using purposive sampling technique with Pondok Pesantren Sumber Pendidikan Agama Allah (SPMAA) of East Java, Indonesia as a research object. The theoretical basis used in this research is the theory of the hidden curriculum and eco pesantren (pesantren who care about the environment).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Hidden Curriculum Shapes Character in Students

The implementation of education in formal schools and Pondok Pesantren requires planning.

Educational planning is arranged in a curriculum. In general, the curriculum is defined as a set of plans and arrangements regarding the content and learning materials and the methods used as guidelines for the implementation of teaching and learning activities.⁶ The actual curriculum is the implementation of the curriculum in the classroom.⁷ While the hidden curriculum becomes an implementation of the formation of scientific attitudes outside the classroom. Hidden Curriculum has an accidental element because the hidden curriculum is accidentally present at the same time the actual curriculum is implemented.⁸ Discussing the formation of character with education, the right curriculum is a hidden curriculum.

The term "Hidden Curriculum" was introduced by Philip Jackson. This type of curriculum can communicate social values implicitly through formal school policies and the informal school community.⁹ For example, the way students answer questions, how to respect the asatidz (teacher), discipline in learning, cheating, mentoring themselves and others.¹⁰ There are several components in the hidden curriculum. Here are the hidden curriculum components:

⁶ Binti Nasukah, "Peran Budaya Sekolah sebagai Hidden Curriculum Pembentuk Karakter Lulusan Lembaga Pendidikan Islam" *ISSN : 2548-6896*.

⁷ Adlan Fauzi Lubis, *Tesis: Hidden Curriculum dan Pembentukan Karakter*, (Jakarta: UIN Jakarta, 2015) :26.

⁸ Binti Nasukah, Loc.Cit.,

⁹ Kevin Nobel Kurniawan, "Tolerance Education in the Hidden Curriculum: A Case Study on Indonesian Public School", *MASYARAKAT Jurnal Sosiologi* Vol. 23, No. 1, (Januari 2018): 1-30

¹⁰ Fathurrohman, "Konservasi Pendidikan Karakter Islam dalam Hidden Curriculum Sekolah", *Jurnal Pendidikan Agama* Vol 02 No 01, (Mei, 2014), : 132-143.

Figure 1. Components of the Hidden Curriculum Source: (Kurniawan, 2018)

From the discussion on, it can be concluded that the hidden curriculum in its implementation focuses more on habitus in educational institutions. The hidden curriculum is carried out outside of the lesson; the implementation can be as a habit of the pesantren, school rules for the behavior exemplified by the teacher/ustadz. Habitus is carried out continuously during the education period so that it will form habits of individuals. In other words, habitus can form characters.

The character is a basic value that builds a person's personality, is formed either because of the influence of heredity or environmental influences and is manifested in attitudes and behavior in everyday life.¹¹ A person's character can be formed through education. Character education is a process of character building that involves aspects of knowledge, aspects of feelings and aspects of the action.¹²

The hidden curriculum is all aspects of experience gained by students in schools or boarding schools that are very influential on the character of students.¹³ This can be both positive and negative. Depends on what experience students get. For example, if students get the habit of getting up early and praying, throwing garbage in its place, it becomes a positive habit.

This habit is capable of forming the character of students. Include shaping environmental awareness character. Incorporating environmental education in a hidden curriculum is an effective way of shaping the environmental awareness character of santri or students.

3.2. Hidden Curriculum as an Effective Way to Shapes Environmental Awareness

According to previous research, Pesantren SPMAA that implements an eco-pesantren system.¹⁴ Pesantren SPMAA provides a learning model of environmental education based on hidden curriculum based on the theory that is inserted into some subjects and practice-based as a form of habituation. According to an indicator of eco

¹¹ Esti Rahmah Pratiwi, *Pengaruh Kurikulum tersembunyi (Hidden Curriculum) Terhadap Pembentukan Karakter Siswa Kelas VIII di SMP IT Masjid Syuhada' Kotabaru Yogyakarta.* (Yogyakarta: UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta, 2016): 42

¹² Esti Rahmah Pratiwi, *Ibid.*,

¹³ Esti Rahmah Pratiwi, *Ibid.*,

¹⁴ Rihlah Nur Aulia, et al, "Pengelolaan Lingkungan Berbasis Pesantren: Studi Kasus di Pondok Pesantren SPMAA Lamongan, Jawa Timur" *Jurnal PLPB* Vol XIX, No 1 e- ISSN : 2580-9199 (Maret, 2018): 73-88

pesantren,¹⁵ Pesantren SPMAA eco-pesantren system. Researchers conclude from environmental awareness results on students from the implementation of hidden environment-based curriculum in the Pondok Pesantren SPMAA which is connected to the hidden curriculum component.

The analysis will be divided into three parts: one part on the components of the hidden curriculum, one on eco pesantren on Pesantren SPMAA, and one on the result of environmental awareness. In the leadership and management component, the environmental awareness generated can be in the form of a natural caring attitude when building. Curriculum and teaching components will form scientific characters. This means that santri understand the urgency, impact, virtues, and methods of environmental conservation. In the cultural component, santri/students will have an attitude of protecting the environment such as throwing trash in a place, sorting trash, and imitating good things exemplified by Ustadz. The student activity component will produce a skillful attitude in using and processing natural resources. Components of communication of wider community will result in caring for students.

¹⁵ Rihlah Nur Aulia, et al, Konsep Ecopesantren dalam Menjawab Degradasi Lingkungan, Seminar Nasional dalam Rangka Dies Natalis UNJ ke-53, (Jakarta; Laboratorium Sosial Politik Press UNJ, 2017)

4. Summary

Environmental degradation is a serious matter that must be handled by all parties of the world. Many ways have been done regarding environmental awareness campaigns. However, environmental degradation has even become a major contemporary issue. In other words, it is necessary to overcome solution innovations and prevent environmental degradation. The solution innovation offered is to establish environmental awareness through the hidden curriculum at Pondok Pesantren. The hidden curriculum is carried out outside of the lesson; the implementation can be as a habit of the pesantren, school rules for the behavior exemplified by the teacher /Ustadz. Habitus is carried out continuously during the education period so that it will form habits of individuals. This habit is capable of forming the character of students. Include shaping environmental awareness character. Incorporating environmental education in the hidden curriculum is an effective way of shaping the environmental awareness of character of students or students.

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